

Big Data Ethics

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Abstract—over the past ten years, data has grown on the Internet, and we are the fuel and haste of this increase. Business owners, they produce apps for us, and we feed these companies with our data, unfortunately, it is all our private data. In the end, we become, through our private data, a commodity that is sold to the highest bidder.

Without security, not even privacy. Ethical oversight and constraints are needed to ensure that an appropriate balance. This article will cover: the contents of big data, what it includes, how data is collected, and the process of involving it on the Internet. In addition, it discuss the analysis of data, methods of collecting it, and factors of ethical challenges. Furthermore, the user's rights, which must be observed, and the privacy the user has.

Keywords—Organize big data, classification, Security, safety, Privacy of use, privacy of the societies, Privacy standards, Security, Artificial intelligence applications, analyze and identify laws and regulations, Data redundancy, availability.

I. INTRODUCTION

We all have our own content on the Internet. Without exception, every human being has data available, perhaps for governments, institutions, or private companies. Big Data is all about capturing, storing, sharing, evaluating, and acting upon information that humans and devices create and distribute using computer-based technologies and networks.

We never, ever in the history of humankind have had access to so much information so quickly and so easily. Data comes from a multitude of sources, including sensors used to gather climate information, posts to social media sites, digital pictures and videos, purchase transaction records, RFID devices, and cell phone GPS signals to name a few. (Herschel, R. and V.M. Miori. 2017) Over the past ten years, data has grown on the Internet, and the humanity plays role for this increase.

This transformation is comparable to the Industrial Revolution in the ways our previous big data society will be left radically changed. Indeed, big data is very big business. Though big data has been commercialized elsewhere, little scholarly attention has been given to the ways in which large data resources have come to bear upon industrial. For example, industrial agriculture, often called “data-driven farming” or “smart farming”.

When applied to collegiate administration, this raises several ethical questions, including:

What, specifically, is the role of big data in education?

How can big data enrich the student experience?

Is it possible to use big data to increase retention?

To what extent can big data contribute to successful outcomes?

More specifically, we must ask what it means to “know” with predictive analytics. Furthermore, once an administration “knows” something about student performance, what ethical obligations follow.

The potential for social change means that we are now at a critical moment; big data uses today will be sticky and will settle both default norms and public notions of what is “no big deal” regarding big data predictions for years to come (Richards, N.M. and J.H. King 2014). Also, since there is no absolute authority to whom we can appeal for guidance, it is important that we, the data creators, suppliers, and users, should engage with these ethical considerations.

Business owners produce applications for users, and the public support these companies with data. Unfortunately, it is the users' private data. In the end, it became a commodity for the one who pays a high price. The issue here that, it is without security and privacy for people rights. Many people are shocked when they know that someone else knows the details of their life. He may have forgotten that he was the one who told others these details on social media. Public, as well as private, data are downloaded and uploaded. In fact, all of our data is private, including name, surname, and even date of birth. Noting that, societies must bear responsibility for the data that circulate, and for long periods.

The reason is that the videos, pictures and news that are being published now will affect the future, and the future of generations, positively and negatively. This technology is posing concerns mainly children. The novelty of Big Data poses ethical difficulties (such as for privacy). Moreover, perhaps, it will become one of the customs of the people, and it may reach that it is one of its values and customs.

A fundamental aspect of this is that one does not know, indeed cannot know, how data will be used in the future, or what other data they will be linked with. This means we cannot usefully characterize data sets as public (vs. not public) or by potential use (since these are unlimited and unforeseeable), and that the intrinsic nature of the data cannot be used as an argument that they are not risky. It is not the data per se that raise ethical issues, but the use to which they are put and the analysis to which they are subjected (H Hand, D.J. 2018).

Due to aspects such as security, privacy, compliance issues, and ethical use, data oversight can be a challenging affair. However, the management problems of big data become bigger due to the unpredictable and unstructured nature of the data. Drowning in data? Unable to derive

valuable insights from your big data siloes? We will highlights the top big data challenges and how you can solve them.

Managing Voluminous Data: The speed at which big data is being created is quickly surpassing the rate at which computing and storage systems are being developed.

What Is Unstructured Data?

Unstructured data is basically data that cannot be easily stored in the traditional column-row database or spreadsheets such as Microsoft Excel table. For these reasons, it becomes extremely difficult to analyze, besides being difficult to search. With all these challenges, it explains why, until recently, organizations didn't consider unstructured data of any use.

Figure 1 Structured and unstructured data

II. USE BIG DATA

Nowadays data is available in a wide range than before. (Al-Jarrah, O. Yoo, P. Muhaidat, S. Karagiannidis, G. 2015). Big data is neither artificial nor fake, and it is the people own real life events. Big data is mostly international, which means that it could be access globally, like in Google.

Big Data encompasses everything from click stream data from the web to genomic and proteomic data from biological research and medicines.

Big Data is a heterogeneous mix of data both structured (traditional datasets –in rows and columns like DBMS tables, CSV's and XLS's) and unstructured data like e-mail attachments, manuals, images, PDF documents, medical records such as x-rays, ECG and MRI images, forms, rich media like graphics, video and audio, contacts, forms and documents.

Businesses are primarily concerned with managing unstructured data, because over 80 percent of enterprise data is unstructured and require significant storage space and effort to manage. “Big data” refers to datasets whose size is beyond the ability of typical database software tools to capture, store, manage, and analyses.

Big data analytics is the area where advanced analytic techniques operate on big data sets. It is about two things. Big data and Analytics, and how the two have teamed up to create one of the most profound trends in business intelligence. Map Reduce by itself is capable for analyzing large distributed data sets; but due to the heterogeneity, velocity and volume of Big Data, it is a challenge for traditional data analysis and management tools. A problem with Big Data is that they use NoSQL and has no Data Description Language (DDL) and it

supports transaction processing. In addition, web-scale data is not universal and it is heterogeneous. For analysis of Big Data, database integration and cleaning is much harder than the traditional mining approaches. Parallel processing and distributed computing is becoming a standard procedure which are nearly non-existent in RDBMS (Duggal, P.S. and S. Paul. (2013)).

When combined with analytics and data mining, Big Data provides new opportunities for understanding and predicting consumer behavior ... and more. Firms are using Big Data to enhance their relationships with existing customers and to exploit opportunities to attract new customers. In addition, Big Data is being analyzed to better manage supply chains, health care, to monitor equipment and facilities, and to create new products and services or to enhance existing ones.

However, this relatively new ability to capture, share, analyze, and act upon a wealth of new data is not without potential risk for firms and their customers (Herschel, R. and V.M. Miori. 2017).

Companies who works on big data analysis are always cause-based on internet survey (Khayyam, H. Jamali, A. Bab-Hadiashar, oftentimes Big Data is difficult to manage and it is often incomplete or even inaccurate.

Yet it is also rich and easily and continuously available in huge volumes for analysis. Because the nature of Big Data is so indiscriminate, firms may be privy to information that they never intentionally intended to collect. In other words, Big Data may incorporate information that infringes upon people's privacy. (A. Esch, T. Ramakrishna, S. Jalili, M. Naebe, M. 2020).

Economic entities and not only, had developed over the years new and more complex methods that allows them to see market evolution, their position on the market, the efficiency of offering their services and/or products etc. For being able to accomplish that, a huge volume of data is needed in order to be mined so that can generate valuable insights. Every year the data transmitted over the internet is growing exponentially. By the end of 2016, Cisco estimates that the annual global data traffic will reach 6.6. zettabytes. The challenge will be not only to “speed up” the internet connections, but also to develop software systems that will be able to handle large data requests in optimal time. To have a better understanding of what Big Data means, the table below represents a comparison between traditional data and Big Data.

Traditional Data	Big Data
Documents	Photos
Finances	Audio and Video
Stock Records	3D Models
Personnel files	Simulations
	Location data

Table 1 Understanding Big Data

This example provides information about the volume and the variety of Big Data. It is difficult to work with complex information on standard database systems or on personal computers. Usually it takes parallel software systems and infrastructure that can handle the process of sorting the amount of information. The request for more complex information is getting higher every year. Streaming information in real-time is becoming a challenge that must be

overcome by those companies that provides such services, in order to maintain their position on the market.

By collecting data in a digital form, companies take their development to a new level. Analyzing digital data can speed the process of planning and also can reveal patterns that can be further used in order to improve strategies. Receiving information in real-time about customer needs is useful for seeing market trends and forecasting (Tole, A.A., 2013).

The usage and valuing data through artificial intelligence, and machine learning helps them a lot. Data multiplicity in the web will change human behavior and the development of technology in the world (Radwan N. 2020).

Discovery analytics against big data can be enabled by different types of analytic tools, including those based on data mining, statistical analysis, fact clustering, data visualization, natural language processing, text analytics, and artificial intelligence. A unique challenge for researchers system and academicians is that the large datasets needs special processing systems. They gives Data Scientists the techniques through which analysis of Big Data can be done (Duggal, P.S. and S. Paul. 2013).

Beneficiary members like governments and companies work on collecting data. Cukier (2013) said: " The ethical challenges of big data have increased, due to several factors including": Users and companies who collect big data, produce a new generation of building based on available evidence. The predictive analysis has an impact on research, perpetuating old and past beliefs.

Using of Big Data necessarily requires skepticism and caution to avoid statistical false positives and incorrect findings that may lead to bad decisions and unintended risk for both the organizations and its customers (Herschel, R. and V.M. Miori. 2017).

III. LITERATURE

The big data market is an industry that is expected to grow enormously into the future and offers the economy (business and government) great potential. The histogram in Figure 1 shows a revenue forecast for the global big data industry from 2018 to 2026.

Figure 2 Big Data Market

The bulk of big data generated comes from three primary sources: social data, Internet of Things and transactional data. Two of the largest sources are:

1. **Transactional data**, including everything from stock prices to bank data to individual merchants'

purchase histories, payment orders, storage records, delivery receipts, etc.

2. **Internet of Things (Industry 4.0)** is a combination of embedded technologies regarding wired and wireless communications, sensor and actuator devices, and the physical objects connected to the Internet.

In the coming years, 40% of the total data created will be from sensors. This includes sensors in smart cities, phones, cars, robots, medical devices, road cameras, satellites, location data on cell phone networks, games, and instantaneous electrical usage in homes and businesses, but also large-scale industry machines like power grids, airplanes, etc. According to various forecasts, around 25-50 billion devices are expected to be connected to the Internet by 2020.

Big Data includes procurement, storing, mining, editing, representing data. Analytics includes analysis, reviewing, explanation. Technologists often use the technical definition of big data as "high-volume, high-velocity and high-variety information assets that demand cost-effective, innovative forms of information processing for enhanced insight and decision making." (Richards, N.M. and J.H. King. 2014).

The analyst has to be careful when using big data; keep in mind big data always has its inconsistencies. For instance, social participation between individuals, a group of people may participate in a specific level of interest, despite the absence of social ties between them, or their various social, cultural or professional levels (Liu, Y. Bi, S. Shi, Z. Hanzo, L. 2019). This sharing results in a graphical imbalance, produces an inaccurate analysis through their connection to a shared virtual world.

Corporate ownership for the Internet usage policy will be changed in the near future, and big companies with big data will sell this data. As for the memory of big data, the data will be saved and stored, using multiple memories, and this method is being used by the operating companies, wherefore it allows others to access the history and privacy of the user, and the graded of his changes through his life.

There are legitimate but unethical ways to collect data. once a user allows companies to access the user's data, it gives them the permission to partially access data.

The smart programs begin to analyze and link the user's information, and observe the user's movements, to form a complete identity about him, while he does not know. Such as determining the location, operating the front camera, and following his interests in surfing the Internet. We prefer to define big data and big data analytics socially, rather than technically, in terms of the broader societal impact they will have.

Mayer-Schönberger, V. Cukier, (2013) define big data as referring "to things one can do at a large scale that cannot be done at a smaller one, to extract new insights or create new forms of value, in ways that change markets, organizations, the relationship between citizens and governments, and more."

We have some reservations about using the term "big data" at all, as it can exclude important parts of the problem, such as decisions made on small data sets, or focus us on the size of the data set rather than the importance of decisions made based upon inferences from data.

Perhaps “data analytics” or “data science” are better terms, but we will use the term “big data” (to denote the collection and storage of large data sets) and “big data analytics” (to denote inferences and predictions made from large data (Richards, N.M. and J.H. King 2014). Moreover, the usage of free social applications taxes at the expense of saving private user’s data. If the user refuses to provide his private data to the operator, he will be deprived from using the free applications.

Figure 3 Things that happen on internet every 60 seconds

Sometimes, scientific, social, cultural or political studies which rely entirely on the big data which is available on the Internet may have incorrect results. It is clear that as a result of the big data which is available online, there is a price to access this data. As is the case with the money kept in the bank, there are banks which have a sensitive data, and companies resorted to keep their big data in available memory. So every user should be careful because his data can be used for illegal purposes. Through the availability of big data among companies (Lin, W. Yip, N. Ho, J. Sambasivan, M. 2020), it has become possible to convert it to a successful and effective project, a good example is Google and Face book (Liu, Y. Bi, S. Shi, Z. Hanzo, L. 2019).

Studies and researches which have been conducted on this issue declared that there must be a permission from its owner, and this is what has been done in the current century (Tybout & Zaltman, 1974). The permission for collecting user’s information must be known, through the cookie, and given the right to accept or reject (Markham, A. Tiidenberg, K. 2018). On the other hand, Companies which provide free services have the right to take the benefit from the big data that they have. However, the user has the right to have the option of accepting or rejecting whether his data being used or not for researches, statistical, or even commercial purposes. In another case, the user may fall into a dilemma from using free applications, on giving his acceptance for giving the operator the right to own his data.

One of the most important user rights that must be observed is the ability to remove, add, modify, and this is true. The user may need to request access to his personal data, whenever he wants, (username or password for example), as it is obtained after verification, building trust relationship, knowing that it is stored and saved for him, Lewis (2012:11). Data expiration, and this is a right, as data is cancelled,

removed or destroyed, if it has not been used for a very long time, and commercial companies do not want to keep this large amount of data unused, and useless, (Nunan, D. Domenico, M. 2013). So as not to pile up and flab off.

IV. PROPOSED TECHNIQUE

One important thing is privacy; It is not permissible, and illegal to use information, pictures and data, without obtaining the permission of its owner. When using big data, operators (companies) must take in consideration the needs of individuals, when using their data, and help them to access their accounts.

This happens when checking the user’s identity. According to Zwitter (2014), major ethical themes: Privacy: Prior permission must be obtained, upon exposure to personal information (Nunan, D. Domenico, M. 2013). Also, for the user’s rights, security: Mechanism and algorithms must be put in place to maintain external threats to data (Markham, A. Tiidenberg, K. 2018). Ownership: There is a right of ownership of personal data (Nunan, D. Domenico, M. 2013). Decision building based on available evidence (Tene & Polonetsky, 2013, p.253).

Three axes, in the big data:

1. Organize big data, classification, and enforcement of laws, regulations, and method of use.
2. Privacy of use, and permission from its owner.
3. Security, safety, and the right to amend or even delete from its owner.

In addition to, the advantages and disadvantages of Big Data, for each one. Artificial intelligence applications have entered all industries.

Through these smart programming, it was able to analyze and identify the strengths and weaknesses of the data owner.

Unfortunately, until now, there are no laws and regulations that determine the way to use this data, even if it is not available for others.

Data redundancy, availability pollution occurs, and we need devices with high memory.

- Privacy, whereby private things from an individual's life are preserved and withheld from others.
- The privacy of the societies, such as interests, hobbies, style and lifestyle, and societal details
- Future expectations, a prediction of what will happen to people or societies.
- Privacy standards, ethics and rules of research ethics, through the applications of social media.
 1. Security: Mechanism and algorithms must be put in place to maintain external threats to data.
 2. There are a security aspects that must be taken into account, and taken into consideration.
 3. For example, entry method, verification mechanism, and trust.

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